

Co-ordination Chemistry of Quinquevalent Molybdenum Oxopentabromo Molybdates (V)

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In continuation of our investigations on the co-ordination chemistry¹⁻³ of quinquevalent molybdenum we report here for the first time the isolation of a few salts of the hypothetical oxypentabromo molybdic(V) acid with organic bases, like, ethylenediamine, propylene diamine, triethylene tetramine, 2,2' bipyridyl and 1,10 phenanthroline etc. Salts of other bases have been reported by previous workers⁴⁻⁶. We have isolated these salts in pure state by modifying the method of Weinland and Knoll⁴. The salts have been characterised by analytical methods, magnetic measurements and determination of oxidation states by ceric sulphate titration. The metal is in quinquevalent state in these compounds. Method of analysis is almost similar as described previously¹. Magnetic measurements were made with Guoy balance at a field strength 8500 gauss and the values calculated using the formula $\mu_{\text{eff}} = 2.839 (X'_M \cdot T)^{\frac{1}{2}}$ B. M. where X'_M = Molar susceptibility after diamagnetic correction and T = absolute temperature. The results are given in Table 1.

TABLE I

Compounds	Color	Mo (%)	Br (%)	N (%)	μ_{eff}	
2 : 2' Bipyridyl Oxopentabromo molybdate (V) $C_{10}H_{10}N_2M_0OBr_5$	Yellowish brown	Found	14.11%	60.52	4.70	1.83
		Calc.	14.32	59.70	4.19	
1 : 10 Phenanthroline Oxopentabromo molybdate (V) $C_{12}H_{10}N_3M_0OBr_5$	Light green	Found	13.94	57.07	4.13	1.82
		Calc.	13.84	57.62	4.03	
Ethylenediamine Oxopentabromo molybdate (V) $C_7H_{10}N_2M_0OBr_5$	Reddish brown	Found	16.91	69.40	4.69	1.73
		Calc.	16.73	69.70	4.88	
Propylenediamine Oxopentabromo molybdate (V) $C_8H_{12}N_2M_0OBr_5$	Greenish yellow	Found	16.45	68.79	4.95	1.72
		Calc.	16.33	68.03	4.77	
Triethylenetetramine Oxopentabromo molybdate (V) $C_6H_{16}N_4M_0OBr_5 \cdot 2HBr$	Brownish yellow	Found	11.91	68.03	6.43	1.69
		Calc.	11.68	68.13	6.82	

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Magnetic susceptibility data are in excellent agreement with the "spin only" value for d' configuration of quinquevalent molybdenum which is also substantiated by oxidation state determination.

Detailed investigations of these salts together with the isolation of the free acid and other salts of organic bases like, aniline, oxine, triethanolamine etc. and also of hydroxylamine and hydrazine are in progress which will be published in due course.

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